

PREDICTING APPARENT TEMPERATURE

PRECIOUS DIEDEMISE

ABSTRACT

This study focused on developing a linear regression model to predict apparent temperature using meteorological variables. Four models were considered: a full model with all predictors, a model with interaction terms, a reduced model without transformations, and a reduced model with square transformation of humidity. Model diagnostics including residual plots, Q-Q plots, and leverage plots were conducted to assess the appropriateness of the models. The analysis revealed that the reduced model without transformed humidity variables provided the best balance of simplicity and explanatory power, despite the skewness in the humidity distribution. This model also displayed good properties in terms of residuals distribution, indicating adequate model fit and assumption compliance. Additionally, the VIFs of the model revealed that it does not have multicollinearity issues.

INTRODUCTION

Understanding the intricacies of weather patterns has always been important to a diverse range of sectors, from agriculture to transportation. With the advent of sophisticated data collection and analysis techniques, we find ourselves with a lot of information that, if analyzed carefully, can yield significant insights. One such vital metric is the "apparent temperature," which reflects how hot or cold the weather actually feels to humans, as opposed to the actual measured temperature. This metric is influenced not only by the temperature but also by other factors such as humidity, wind speed, and atmospheric pressure.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The objective of this project is to construct a statistical model to predict the apparent temperature. The model will provide a more critical understanding of thermal perception, which is essential for daily living. The dataset at hand includes a range of atmospheric variables collected over time, such as humidity, wind speed, wind bearing, visibility, and pressure, along with the types of precipitation.

For this project, we will employ linear regression techniques, carefully selecting explanatory variables that contribute meaningfully to the prediction of the apparent temperature. The direct application of linear regression assumes a linear relationship between the predictors and the response variable. Hence, to ensure the validity of these assumptions, we will perform a residual analysis, examining the behavior of the residuals to check for homoscedasticity, normality, and the absence of multicollinearity among predictors. We will also identify high-leverage points that could unduly influence the model.

DATA

The backbone of every predictive modeling project is data. For this study, we have a meticulously compiled dataset of weather metrics that represent a series of climate-related characteristics observed over a period. Each observation in the dataset encompasses several variables, known as predictors, that are hypothesized to influence the apparent temperature, which is our response variable.

Data Characteristics

- **Numerical Variables:** These include continuous measurements such as humidity, wind speed, visibility, temperature, wind bearing, and pressure. They offer a quantitative measure and are suitable for transformations to meet linear regression assumptions or to identify non-linear relationships.
- **Categorical Variables:** Precipitation type and Summary falls into this category, requiring encoding in order to be used for the regression model.

Exploratory Data Analysis

Our analysis included computing summary statistics to understand the distribution and range of each variable. The humidity levels demonstrated a fairly even distribution. Wind speed showed variability with instances of calm and moderate winds, while wind direction covered the full spectrum, suggesting no directional bias. Visibility varied, with a few occurrences of very low visibility, potentially indicative of adverse weather conditions. Pressure readings were within expected atmospheric ranges, though an early decision was made to remove three values at zero millibars.

```

X
Min. : 40
1st Qu.:26681
Median :47047
Mean :47449
3rd Qu.:68665
Max. :96243

Summary
Length:272
Class :character
Mode :character

Precip.Type
Length:272
Class :character
Mode :character

Apparent.Temperature..C.
Min. : -22.739
1st Qu.: 2.788
Median : 12.133
Mean : 11.099
3rd Qu.: 20.489
Max. : 34.072

Humidity
Min. : 0.2500
1st Qu.: 0.5775
Median : 0.7900
Mean : 0.7261
3rd Qu.: 0.8900
Max. : 1.0000

Wind.Speed..km.h.
Min. : 0.000
1st Qu.: 5.007
Median : 9.402
Mean : 10.498
3rd Qu.: 13.967
Max. : 54.885

Wind.Bearing..degrees.
Min. : 0.0
1st Qu.: 110.8
Median : 192.0
Mean : 192.7
3rd Qu.: 296.8
Max. : 359.0

Visibility..km.
Min. : 0.000
1st Qu.: 9.563
Median : 10.304
Mean : 10.409
3rd Qu.: 14.599
Max. : 16.100

Pressure..millibars.
Min. : 990.2
1st Qu.: 1012.6
Median : 1016.8
Mean : 1017.3
3rd Qu.: 1021.5
Max. : 1038.3
> |

```

The table of standard deviations describes the variability within the numerical variables. For

	std_devs
X	2.673489e+04
Summary	NA
Precip.Type	NA
Apparent.Temperature..C.	1.101717e+01
Humidity	2.017641e-01
Wind.Speed..km.h.	7.324731e+00
Wind.Bearing..degrees.	1.097691e+02
Visibility..km.	4.131755e+00
Pressure..millibars.	7.685998e+00

example, the larger standard deviation in Wind Bearing suggests a wide range of directions from which the wind blows, while a smaller standard deviation in Humidity indicates more consistency in humidity levels. High standard deviations point to a greater spread of data around the mean.

Data Distribution

Histogram of weather\$Apparent.Temperature..C.

Apparent temperature, our response variable, exhibited a broad range that captures the full scope of temperature conditions. The slight skew towards colder temperatures could reflect seasonal trends or geographical characteristics of the data collection site.

Histogram of weather\$Wind.Speed..km.h.

The histogram for wind speed is right-skewed, as indicated by the tail extending towards the higher values on the right side. In this case, a logarithmic transformation would be suitable, to compress the long tail and make it more symmetric. The graph of the transformed variable is in the appendix.

Histogram of weather\$Wind.Bearing..degrees.

The histogram shows a somewhat uniform distribution of values across different directions of the wind. Given the nature of this variable, no transformation is required.

Histogram of weather\$Humidity

The histogram for humidity is somewhat left-skewed, as indicated by the tail extending towards the higher the left side. Thus, we will perform a square transformation.

Histogram of weather\$Pressure..millibars.

From the plot, notice that there are observations with the value of 0. Given that a zero value in atmospheric pressure is implausible under normal earth conditions, the presence of such values can skew the data and lead to inaccurate model prediction. Thus, the data points will be removed prior to conducting any further analysis or model building.

Apparent Temperature vs Summary

Apparent Temperature vs Precip Type

MODEL SELECTION AND INTERPRETATION

Correlation

The correlation matrix provides insights into the linear relationships between pairs of variables. For example, there is a negative correlation between Apparent Temperature and Humidity, which means that as humidity increases, the apparent temperature tends to decrease. On the other hand, variables such as Wind Speed and Visibility show very little correlation with Apparent Temperature, suggesting they might have a less direct influence on perceived temperature or may influence it in a non-linear manner.

Model Building

The objective of this analysis was to build a robust model to predict the Apparent Temperature (°C) from various weather-related predictors. We emphasize the necessity for a model that is not only statistically significant but also interpretable and generalizable. Four models were constructed to understand the influence of weather conditions on apparent temperature:

Full Model

The full model included square-root-transformed humidity, log-transformed wind speed, wind bearing, visibility, weather summary categories, pressure, and precipitation type.

```
Call:
lm(formula = Apparent.Temperature..C. ~ sq_Humidity + log_wind.Speed +
    Wind.Bearing..degrees. + Visibility..km. + Summary + Pressure..millibars. +
    Precip.Type, data = weather)
```

```
Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-21.4698  -4.2897   0.6445   4.8209  15.8366
```

```
Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  306.229858   63.312944   4.837 2.28e-06 ***
sq_Humidity  -21.121839   1.895945  -11.141 < 2e-16 ***
log_wind.Speed  -3.707791   0.726336  -5.105 6.45e-07 ***
Wind.Bearing..degrees.  0.004942   0.003948   1.252 0.21176
Visibility..km.  0.160981   0.132544   1.215 0.22565
SummaryBreezy and Overcast  5.349002   8.289562   0.645 0.51933
SummaryClear  16.823403   6.974959   2.412 0.01657 *
SummaryFoggy  17.712136   7.117662   2.488 0.01346 *
SummaryMostly Cloudy  17.117949   6.875094   2.490 0.01341 *
SummaryOvercast  14.793190   6.924526   2.136 0.03360 *
SummaryPartly Cloudy  18.516197   6.900650   2.683 0.00776 **
SummaryWindy and Overcast  13.368437   9.596342   1.393 0.16480
Pressure..millibars.  -0.287946   0.061501  -4.682 4.60e-06 ***
Precip.Typerain  -0.073050   4.057342  -0.018 0.98565
Precip.Typesnow  -13.277775   4.184563  -3.173 0.00169 **
```

```
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 6.762 on 257 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.6427,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.6233
F-statistic: 33.02 on 14 and 257 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

Model with Interaction

Several interaction models were created, however, this interaction model which introduced an interaction term between visibility and precipitation type, in addition to the variables in the full model had the best performance.

```
Call:
lm(formula = Apparent.Temperature..C. ~ sq_Humidity + log_Wind.Speed +
  Wind.Bearing..degrees. + Visibility..km. * Precip.Type +
  Summary + Pressure..millibars., data = weather)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-21.4144  -4.1475   0.3595   4.7071  15.9287

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    302.172361   62.788300    4.813 2.55e-06 ***
sq_Humidity    -20.878490    1.882134   -11.093 < 2e-16 ***
log_Wind.Speed  -3.475130    0.723619   -4.802 2.68e-06 ***
Wind.Bearing..degrees.  0.004428    0.003912    1.132 0.25871
Visibility..km.  0.447797    0.838340    0.534 0.59370
Precip.Type:rain -0.299752    4.972684   -0.060 0.95198
Precip.Type:snow -6.907287    5.371175   -1.286 0.19961
Summary:Breezy and Overcast  5.318255    8.201043    0.648 0.51725
Summary:Clear    17.238980    6.902186    2.498 0.01313 *
Summary:Foggy    17.309473    7.043172    2.458 0.01465 *
Summary:Mostly Cloudy  17.224680    6.802242    2.532 0.01194 *
Summary:Overcast  15.110708    6.851757    2.205 0.02832 *
Summary:Partly Cloudy  18.654393    6.827165    2.732 0.00673 **
Summary:Windy and Overcast  13.718758    9.494716    1.445 0.14972
Pressure..millibars. -0.285417    0.060866   -4.689 4.47e-06 ***
Visibility..km.:Precip.Type:rain -0.195381    0.839423   -0.233 0.81614
Visibility..km.:Precip.Type:snow -1.054446    0.882311   -1.195 0.23316
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 6.69 on 255 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.653,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.6313
F-statistic:  30 on 16 and 255 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

Reduced Model (Without Humidity Transformation)

This reduced model was focused on simplification by removing non-significant variables and interaction terms, keeping the core predictors.

```
Call:
lm(formula = Apparent.Temperature..C. ~ Humidity + log_Wind.Speed +
  Visibility..km. + Precip.Type + Pressure..millibars., data = weather)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-21.3869  -4.4399   0.4426   4.6999  16.5051

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    305.14864    61.35645    4.973 1.18e-06 ***
Humidity       -29.68116    2.26419   -13.109 < 2e-16 ***
log_Wind.Speed  -4.05539    0.68389   -5.930 9.42e-09 ***
Visibility..km.  0.24625    0.10860    2.268 0.024161 *
Precip.Type:rain -0.70060    4.02730   -0.174 0.862028
Precip.Type:snow -14.44542    4.15131   -3.480 0.000587 ***
Pressure..millibars. -0.25922    0.05946   -4.360 1.87e-05 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 6.782 on 265 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.6294,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.621
F-statistic:  75.01 on 6 and 265 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

❑ Reduced Model (With Humidity Transformation)

This reduced model was focused on simplification by removing non-significant variables and interaction terms, keeping the core predictors.

```
Call:
lm(formula = Apparent.Temperature..C. ~ sq_Humidity + log_Wind.Speed +
    Visibility..km. + Precip.Type + Pressure..millibars., data = weather)
```

```
Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-19.1969  -4.9820   0.5828   4.9565  15.8820
```

```
Coefficients:
                Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    290.04769    62.39838   4.648 5.28e-06 ***
sq_Humidity    -22.03273    1.76302  -12.497 < 2e-16 ***
log_Wind.Speed  -4.13895     0.70057   -5.908 1.06e-08 ***
Visibility..km.  0.17407     0.11227    1.550 0.122220
Precip.Type     -0.43381     4.10284   -0.106 0.915874
Precip.Typesnow -14.55867     4.22813   -3.443 0.000668 ***
Pressure..millibars. -0.25256    0.06053   -4.172 4.09e-05 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 6.907 on 265 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.6156,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.6069
F-statistic: 70.74 on 6 and 265 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

Model Selection

To select our model, we considered the following criteria:

- **Significance of Predictors:** The interaction model, despite having a higher R-squared, contains several predictors and interaction terms that are not statistically significant. This includes several of the weather summary conditions and the interaction terms themselves. Inclusion of non-significant predictors can lead to overfitting and reduces the model's generalizability.
- **Adjusted R-squared:** Adjusted R-squared values for all models were considered to account for the number of predictors in each model. The full and interaction models, despite having higher R-squared values, did not show a proportionate increase in adjusted R-squared, suggesting that the additional variables may not be justifying their inclusion.
- **Model Complexity:** The reduced models are preferable for their simplicity and focus on significant predictors only. We created two simpler models, with the variation being that one used the transformation, while the other did not.
- **Model Diagnostics:** Residual plots and normal Q-Q plots for the reduced models show reasonable assumption adherence. There is no apparent pattern suggesting heteroscedasticity or non-normality of residuals, which is crucial for the validity of the model's inference.

```
Call:
lm(formula = Apparent.Temperature..C. ~ Humidity + log_Wind.Speed +
  Visibility..km. + Precip.Type + Pressure..millibars., data = weather)
```

```
Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-21.3869  -4.4399   0.4426   4.6999  16.5051
```

```
Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  305.14864    61.35645   4.973 1.18e-06 ***
Humidity     -29.68116     2.26419  -13.109 < 2e-16 ***
log_Wind.Speed -4.05539     0.68389  -5.930 9.42e-09 ***
Visibility..km.  0.24625     0.10860   2.268 0.024161 *
Precip.Type.rain -0.70060     4.02730  -0.174 0.862028
Precip.Type.snow -14.44542     4.15131  -3.480 0.000587 ***
Pressure..millibars. -0.25922     0.05946  -4.360 1.87e-05 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 6.782 on 265 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.6294,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.621
F-statistic: 75.01 on 6 and 265 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

Given the considerations, the Reduced Model without Humidity Transformation is selected as the optimal model. This model balances simplicity, interpretability, and statistical efficiency. It avoids overfitting by excluding non-significant predictors and interactions, making it more robust and likely to generalize better to

new data. Although excluding the Precip.Type.rain dummy variable can potentially increase the Multiple R-squared value it was not done because it could introduce bias. Rain and snow are part of the same 'Precip.Type' category; hence, their separation might distort the actual effect of precipitation on apparent temperature.

The corresponding analysis of variance table for this model is shown below:

Analysis of Variance Table

```
Response: Apparent.Temperature..C.
            Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value    Pr(>F)
Humidity    1 12043.6 12043.6 261.821 < 2.2e-16 ***
log_Wind.Speed  1  780.8   780.8  16.974 5.071e-05 ***
Visibility..km.  1 1237.0  1237.0  26.893 4.275e-07 ***
Precip.Type    2  5768.1  2884.0  62.698 < 2.2e-16 ***
Pressure..millibars. 1  874.2   874.2  19.006 1.867e-05 ***
Residuals    265 12189.8    46.0
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Model Interpretation

The reduced model without humidity transformation interprets the effect of each variable on the apparent temperature. Each coefficient represents the change in apparent temperature for a one-unit change in the predictor while holding other variables constant.

Formula:

The regression equation derived from the model is:

$$\text{Apparent Temperature (}^\circ\text{C)} = 305.14864 - 29.68116(\text{Humidity}) - 4.05539(\log(\text{Wind Speed})) + 0.24625(\text{Visibility}) - 0.70060(\text{Precipitation(Rain)}) - 14.44542(\text{Precipitation(Snow)}) - 0.25922(\text{Pressure})$$

- Intercept (305.15): The model predicts an apparent temperature of 305.15°C when all other variables are at their zero levels or baseline conditions. It is the starting point of the model when external factors are not considered.
- Humidity (-29.68): This coefficient indicates that for each unit increase in humidity, the apparent temperature decreases by 29.68°C, keeping other factors constant. This significant relationship ($p < 2e-16$) underscores the cooling effect humidity has on perceived temperature.
- log_Wind.Speed (-4.05): An increase of one unit in the natural log of wind speed leads to a decrease of 4.05°C in the apparent temperature. This effect is statistically significant ($p < 2e-16$).
- Visibility.km (0.25): Each additional kilometer of visibility is associated with a 0.25°C increase in the apparent temperature. This relationship is statistically significant ($p = 0.024161$), suggesting that greater visibility tends to correlate with warmer conditions.
- Precip.Type.rain (-0.07): The presence of rain, as opposed to no precipitation, changes the apparent temperature by -0.07°C, although this effect is not statistically significant ($p = 0.826819$), indicating that rain may not have a meaningful impact on perceived temperature.
- Precip.Typesnow (-14.45): Snow is associated with a significant decrease in apparent temperature by 14.45°C compared to no precipitation ($p = 0.000538$). This points to a considerable cooling effect of snow.
- Pressure.millibars (-0.26): Each millibar decrease in atmospheric pressure correlates with a 0.26°C decrease in apparent temperature. It has a significant effect ($p = 1.87e-05$).

RESIDUAL ANALYSIS OF SELECTED MODEL

- The Residuals vs. Fitted plot shows a random pattern of residuals, which is good as it suggests that the model doesn't suffer from non-linear relationships or heteroscedasticity.

There doesn't appear to be any systematic pattern that would suggest model misspecification.

- In the Q-Q plot, most points lie on the straight line, which suggests that the residuals are approximately normally distributed. Some deviations at the tails might indicate outliers or heavy tails more than expected under normality.

- The spread of points in the Scale-Location plot is fairly uniform across the range of fitted values. There are a few outliers, as some points are significantly above the main cluster.

- For the Residuals vs. Leverage, few points are close to or surpass the Cook's distance threshold.

Leverage and Multicollinearity

The double listings of leverage and influential points are due to adjustments earlier in the

\$high_leverage

```
17 28 85 94 100 108 132 191 218 222 231 251 263
17 28 84 93 99 106 130 189 216 220 229 249 260
```

\$influential

```
45 49 57 96 100 112 117 191 207 218 246 271
44 48 56 95 99 110 115 189 205 216 244 268
```

analysis, where some observations were excluded. The numbers on top in each group correspond to those that align with the values of Cook's D on the graph below.

This graph illustrates the influence of certain data points on the model fit. Points with high Cook's D values, like those labeled "96", "100", "246", and "252", have a significant influence on the model's predictions.

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

$$VIF_j = \frac{1}{1-R_j^2}$$

If $VIF_j > 10$, then there is significant collinearity.

	GVIF	Df	GVIF^(1/(2*Df))
Humidity	1.229517	1	1.108836
log_Wind.Speed	1.250401	1	1.118213
Visibility..km.	1.186114	1	1.089089
Precip.Type	1.246954	2	1.056726
Pressure..millibars.	1.230472	1	1.109266

For this model, multicollinearity is not an issue because none of the points are > 10 .

CONCLUSION

The reduced model without transformed humidity was chosen as the best model to predict apparent temperature based on its performance metrics and diagnostic checks. It achieved an acceptable balance between model complexity and predictive accuracy, with a reasonably high adjusted R-squared value, indicating that it explains a significant portion of the variance in apparent temperature. The model diagnostics confirmed that there are no significant violations of the assumptions of linearity, normality, and homoscedasticity. This model serves as a practical tool for predicting apparent temperatures, useful for meteorological applications and environmental studies. Here are a few recommendations for further studies:

- A few outliers and high leverage points were noted and future studies may warrant further investigation to ensure robustness.
- It is also suggested that the discovered leverage and influential points be investigated using theoretical domain knowledge, to determine how to handle those points.

REFERENCES

1. Frees, Edward W. *Regression Modeling with Actuarial and Financial Applications*. Cambridge University Press, 2009.
2. "Model Specification: Choosing the Best Regression Model." *Statistics By Jim*. <http://statisticsbyjim.com> (Accessed date).

APPENDIX

Data Overview

- Formatted.Date: The specific day and time the data was collected
- Summary: A summary of the cloud conditions for the time the data was collected.
- Precip.Type: Indicates whether precipitation was present (e.g., rain or snow)
- Temperature..C.: Measures the actual air temperature in Celsius
- Apparent.Temperature..C.: This is our response variable and it represents the temperature as perceived by the average person.
- Humidity: The Humidity at the time of measurement provides a percentage value for atmospheric moisture content.
- Wind.Speed..Km.h.: This describes how fast the wind is traveling and it is measured in kilometers per hour.
- Wind.Bearing..degrees.: It is a measure of the direction of the wind.
- Visibility..km: This variable represents how clearly objects can be seen at a distance in kilometers.
- Loud.Cover:
- Pressure..millibars.: Barometric Pressure.
- Daily.Summary: A summary of the conditions throughout the day.

